

[The latest version of this publication list is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15133615>. This list is updated annually, in April of the year following the version date.]

I. Books

1976

Aspect: An introduction to the study of verbal aspect and related problems (Cambridge Textbooks in Linguistics). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. x + 142 pp.
[Reprinted with corrections 1978, 1981, reprinted 1985, 1987, 1989, 1991, 1993, 1995.
Japanese translation: アスペクト. Tokyo: Mugi Shobo, 227 pp., 1988.
Korean translation: 동사 상의 이해. Korea: Hanshin Publishers, 216 pp., 1998.
Chinese translation: 体范畴. Beijing: Peking University Press, 122 pp., 2016.]

1977

(Bernard Comrie, Norval Smith) *Lingua Descriptive Studies: Questionnaire* (= *Lingua* 42.1). Amsterdam: North-Holland. 72 pp.
[Reprinted 1982 in *International Journal of Dravidian Linguistics* 11: 393–458.
French translation: *Questionnaire structuré pour la description d'une langue*. Montréal: Éditions de l'Université du Québec à Montréal, 98 pp., 1987.
Chinese translation incorporated in: Liu Danqing (ed.), *A handbook for grammatical investigation and research*. Shanghai: Shanghai Educational Publishing House, 2008.]

1978

(Bernard Comrie, Gerald Stone) *The Russian language since the Revolution*. Oxford: Clarendon Press. xii + 258 pp.
[For second edition, see Comrie/Stone/Polinsky 1996.]

1981

Language universals and linguistic typology: Syntax and morphology. Oxford: Blackwell and Chicago: University of Chicago Press. xi + 252 pp.
[Reprinted 1983, 1986, 1987.
Italian translation: *Universali del linguaggio e tipologia linguistica*. Bologna: Il Mulino, 330 pp., 1983.
Spanish translation: *Universales del lenguaje y tipología lingüística: sintaxis y morfología*. Madrid: Gredos, 375 pp., 1988.
Chinese translation: 语言共性和语言类型 (Ershi Shiji Wenku). Beijing: Huaxia Chubanshe, 325 pp., 1989.]

Second revised ed. 1989. Oxford: Blackwell and Chicago: University of Chicago Press. xiv + 264 pp.

[Japanese translation: 言語普遍性と言語類型論: 統語論と形態論. Tokyo: Hituzisyoboo, xiv + 301 pp., 1991.

Turkish translation: *Dil evrensellikleri ve dilbilim tipologisi*. Ankara: HECE. 301 pp., 2005.

Chinese translation: 语言共性和语言类型 (Weiming Translation Library). Beijing: Peking University Press, ix + 315 pp., 2009.

Chinese translation, corrected reprint: 语言共性和语言类型 Shanghai: The Commercial Press, VIII + vii + 349 pp., 2023.]

(Bernard Comrie, in collaboration with B.G. Hewitt, J.R. Payne) *The languages of the Soviet Union*. (Cambridge Language Surveys). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. xxi + 317 pp.

[Digital reprint 2009.]

1985

Tense (Cambridge Textbooks in Linguistics). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. x + 139 pp.

[Reprinted 1986, 1987.

Japanese translation: テンス. Tokyo: Kaitakusha, xv + 271 pp., 2014.]

1996

(Bernard Comrie, Gerald Stone, Maria Polinsky) *The Russian language in the twentieth century*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. xi + 385 pp.

[= Second edition, revised and expanded, of Bernard Comrie and Gerald Stone: *The Russian language since the Revolution*, 1978.]

2001

(Bernard Comrie, Martin Haspelmath) *The Library of Babel*. Berlin: Walter de Gruyter. 23 pp.

[German edition: *Die Bibliothek von Babel*. Berlin: Walter de Gruyter, 2001. 25 pp.; abbreviated version in *Max Planck Forschung* 2/2003: 26–31.]

2002

Sprache und Vorzeit [Language and prehistory] (Sitzungsberichte der Sächsischen Akademie der Wissenschaften zu Leipzig, Philologisch-historische Klasse, Band 137, Heft 6). Leipzig: Verlag der Sächsischen Akademie der Wissenschaften zu Leipzig. 24 pp.

2005

(Enrico Campanile, Bernard Comrie, Calvert Watkins) *Introduzione alla lingua e alla cultura degli Indoeuropei* [*Introduction to the Language and Culture of the Indo-Europeans*]. Bologna: Il Mulino. 144 pp. [Extracted from A. Giacalone Ramat and P. Ramat (eds.), *Le lingue indoeuropee*, 2nd edn., Bologna, 1994: Il Mulino, pp. 19–122.]

2008

Arealtypologie von Sprachen anhand des Weltatlas linguistischer Strukturen. [*Areal typology of languages on the basis of the World Atlas of Language Structures*.] (Sitzungsberichte der Sächsischen Akademie der Wissenschaften zu Leipzig, Philologisch-historische Klasse, Band 140, Heft 3). Leipzig: Verlag der Sächsischen Akademie der Wissenschaften zu Leipzig. 25 pp.

2010

(Bernard Comrie, Madzhid Khalilov) *The dictionary of languages and dialects of the peoples of the Northern Caucasus: Comparison of the basic lexicon*. Leipzig–Makhachkala. 898 pp.

2015

(Bernard Comrie [Komri], Madžid Xalilov, Zaira Xalilova) *Граммати́ка бе́зтинского языка* [*A grammar of Bezhta*]. Leipzig–Makhachkala: Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology and Gamzat Tsadasa Institute for Language, Literature and Arts of the Daghestan Scientific Centre of the Russian Academy of Science. 655 pp.

2020

(Raoul Zamponi, Bernard Comrie) *A grammar of Akabea*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. xv + 440 pp.
Online appendix *Portman's Akabea Dialogues*.
https://fdslive.oup.com/www.oup.com/booksites/uk/booksites/content/9780198855798/Portman's_Akabea_Dialogues.pdf. 172 pp.

2021

(Raoul Zamponi, Bernard Comrie) *A grammar of Akajeru*. (Grammars of World & Minority Languages). London: UCL Press. xi + 171 pp. Open access.
uclpress.co.uk/Akajeru, <https://doi.org/10.14324/111.9781800080935>. List of Addenda and corrigenda available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15029499> (last updated 2026-03-22)

II. Edited Volumes

1978

Classification of grammatical categories (Current Inquiry into Language and Linguistics, 21, Slavic Series, 6; also = *International Review of Slavic Linguistics* 3.1–2). Edmonton: Linguistic Research. vi + 248 pp.

1981

Studies in the languages of the USSR. (Current Inquiry into Language, Linguistics and Human Communication 38; also = *International Review of Slavic Linguistics* 5 (1980).) Edmonton: Linguistic Research.

1984

(Bernard Comrie, Brian Butterworth, Östen Dahl) *Explanations for language universals* (also = *Linguistics* 21). 292 pp. Berlin: Mouton.

1987

The world's major languages. London: Croom Helm and New York: Oxford University Press. xiii + 1025 pp.

[Reprinted 1989.

British paperback editions: *The Major Languages of Western Europe*. London: Routledge, xii + 315 pp., 1990; *The Major Languages of Eastern Europe*. London: Routledge, xii + 255 pp., 1990; *The Major Languages of East and South-East Asia*. London: Routledge, xi + 234 pp., 1990; *The Major Languages of South Asia, the Middle East and Africa*. London: Routledge, xii + 315 pp., 1990.

Malay translation: *Ensiklopedia bahasa utama dunia*. Kuala Lumpur: Dewan Bahasa dan Pustaka, xxxi + 568 pp., 1998.

Second edition: London: Routledge, xvi + 911 pp., 2009.

Third edition: London: Routledge, xvii + 933 pp., 2018.

1988

(Ed. Vladimir P. Nedjalkov; ed. English translation) *Typology of resultative constructions*. (Typological Studies in Language 12.) Amsterdam: John Benjamins. xix, 573 pp.

<https://doi.org/10.1075/tsl.12>

1991

(Bernard Comrie, Mushira Eid) *Perspectives on Arabic linguistics* III. (Current Issues in Linguistic Theory 80.) Amsterdam: John Benjamins. xii + 274 pp.

(Bernard Comrie, Stephen Anderson) *Tense and aspect in eight languages of Cameroon*. (Summer Institute of Linguistics and The University of Texas at Arlington Publications in Linguistics Publication 99.) Dallas: Summer Institute of Linguistics and Arlington: University of Texas at Arlington. xiv + 255 pp.

1993

(Bernard Comrie, Greville G. Corbett) *The Slavonic languages*. London: Routledge. xiii + 1078 pp.

(Bernard Comrie, Maria Polinsky) *Causatives and transitivity*. (Studies in Language Companion Series 23.) Amsterdam: John Benjamins. ix + 399 pp.

1994

(General eds. Christopher Moseley and Ronald E. Asher; section eds. Bernard Comrie; Mary Tait; Terrence Kaufman; Stephen Wurm; Stephen J. Harlow; David Bradley; R. E. Asher; J. Lachlan Mackenzie; A.K. Irvine; Benji Wald). *Atlas of the world's languages*. London: Routledge, viii, 372 pp., 113 maps.

1996

(Bernard Comrie, Stephen Matthews, Maria Polinsky) (consultant eds.). *The atlas of languages: The origin and development of languages throughout the world*. London: Bloomsbury and New York: Facts on File, 224 pp. 1996.

[Dutch translation: *De grote taalAtlas: Oorsprong en ontwikkeling van taal en schrift in de gehele wereld*. Haarlem: Schuyt & Co., 224 pp., 1998.

German translation: *Bildatlas der Sprachen: Ursprung und Entwicklung der Sprachen dieser Erde*. Augsburg: Bechtermünz Verlag, 224 pp., 1998.

Polish translation: *Atlas języków świata: Pochodzenie i rozwój języków świata*. Poznań: Oficyna Wyd. Atena, 224 pp., maps, 1998.

Russian translation: *Атлас языков мира. Происхождение и развитие языков во всем мире*. Moscow: Lik-Press, 224 pp. 1998.

Japanese translation: *世界言語文化図鑑: 世界の言語の起源と伝播*. Tokyo: Toyo Shorin, 225 pp., 1999.

Slovenian translation: *Atlas jezikov: Izvor in razvoj jezikov*. Ljubljana: DZS, 224 pp., 1999.

Portuguese translation: *O atlas das línguas: A origem e a evolução das línguas no mundo*. Lisboa: Estampa, 226 pp., 2001.]

Revised edition: London: Bloomsbury; New York: Facts on File, 224 pp., 2003. Also as *The SBS Atlas of Languages*, ABC Books, Sydney, 240 pp., 2003.

[Croatian translation: *Atlas jezika: Podrijetlo i razvitak jezika u svijetu*. Varaždin: Stanek, 224 pp., 2003.

Greek translation: *Οι γλώσσες του κόσμου: Η καταγωγή και η εξέλιξη των γλωσσών σε ολόκληρο τον πλανήτη*. Athens: Savválas, 224 pp. 2003.

French translation: *Atlas des langues: L'origine et le développement des langues dans le monde*. Paris: Éditions Acropole, 224 pp. 2004.

Japanese translation: 世界言語文化図鑑: 世界の言語の起源と伝播. Tokyo: Toyo Shorin, 225 pp., 2005.

Hungarian translation: *A nyelvek világtalasa: A világ nyelveinek eredete és fejlődése*. Budapest: Kossuth Kiadó, 224 pp., 2006.

Czech translation: *Atlas jazyků: Vznik a vývoj jazyků napříč celým světem*. Praha: Metafora, 224 pp., 2007.]

Persian translation: اطلس زبان ها. Tehran: University of Tehran Press, iv + 214 pp., 2008.]

2000

(Bernard Comrie, Petra Vogel) *Approaches to the typology of word classes*. (Empirical Approaches to Language Typology 23.) Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter. xiii + 514 pp.

2003

(Pirkko Suihkonen, Bernard Comrie) *International Symposium on Deictic Systems and Quantification in Languages Spoken in Europe and North and Central Asia (Udmurt State University, Iževsk, Udmurt Republic, Russia May 22–25, 2001): Collection of papers*. Izhevsk: Udmurt State University / Leipzig: Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology. xvi + 331 pp.

2004

(Bernard Comrie, H. Ekkehard Wolff, guest editors) *The Journal of West African Languages* 30.2. (= Papers from the International Symposium on Areal Typology of West African Languages, Leipzig, Germany, September 1–2, 2000.) West African Linguistic Society. 142 pp.

2005

(Martin Haspelmath, Matthew S. Dryer, David Gil, Bernard Comrie) *The World Atlas of Language Structures*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. xv + 695 pp and CD-ROM.

2006

(Ina Bornkessel, Matthias Schlesewky, Bernard Comrie, Angela D. Friederici) *Semantic role universals and argument linking: Theoretical, typological, and psycholinguistic Perspectives*. Berlin: Walter de Gruyter. viii + 363 pp.

2008

(Robert Nicolaï, Bernard Comrie) *Language contact and the dynamics of language: Theory and implications* (= *Journal of Language Contact* 2.1).

2009

(Bernard Comrie, Ray Fabri, Elizabeth Hume, Manwel Mifsud, Thomas Stolz, Martine Vanhove) *Introducing Maltese linguistics: Selected papers from the 1st International Conference on Maltese Linguistics, Bremen, 18–20 October, 2007*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins. xi + 422 pp.

2010

(Andrej Malchukov, Martin Haspelmath, Bernard Comrie) *Studies in ditransitive constructions: A comparative handbook*. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton. xviii + 772 pp.

2011

(Bernard Comrie, Giuliana Fiorentino) *Nouns and nominalizations cross-linguistically* (= *Italian Journal of Linguistics/Rivista di Linguistica* 23.1). 125 pp.

2012

(Bernard Comrie, Zarina Estrada-Fernández) *Relative clauses in languages of the Americas: A typological overview* (Typological Studies in Language 102). Amsterdam: John Benjamins. xiii + 300 pp.

(Pirkko Suihkonen, Bernard Comrie, Valery Solovyev) *Argument structure and grammatical relations: A cross-linguistic typology* (Studies in Language Companion Series 126). Amsterdam: John Benjamins. xv + 406 pp.

2013

(Claire Lefebvre, Bernard Comrie, Henri Cohen) *New perspectives on the origins of language* (Studies in Language Companion Series 144). Amsterdam: John Benjamins. xvi + 582 pp.

2015

(Bernard Comrie, Lucía Golluscio) *Language contact and documentation/Contacto lingüístico y documentación*. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton. ix + 370 pp.

(N. J. Enfield, Bernard Comrie) *The languages of Mainland Southeast Asia: The State of the Art* (Pacific Linguistics 649). Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton. vi + 662 pp.

(Andrej Malchukov, Bernard Comrie) *Valency classes in the world's languages*. 2 vols. (Comparative Handbooks of Linguistics 1/1–2). Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton. xii + 1721 pp.

2017

(Yoshiko Matsumoto, Bernard Comrie, Peter Sells) *Noun-modifying clause constructions in languages of Eurasia: Rethinking theoretical and geographic boundaries* (Typological Studies in Language 116). Amsterdam: John Benjamins. vi + 381 pp.

2018

(Guus Kroonen, James P. Mallory, Bernard Comrie) *Talking Neolithic: Proceedings of the Workshop on Indo-European Origins held at the Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology, Leipzig, December 2-3, 2013* (Journal of Indo-European Studies, Monograph Series 65.) Washington, DC: Institute for the Study of Man. v + 374 pp.

III. Edited Online Resource

1998-present

Intercontinental Dictionary Series (General Editor; Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology, Leipzig) <<http://ids.clld.org/>>

IV. Articles

1971

Some thoughts on defining the word in phonology. *Papers in Linguistics* 4: 447–461.

1973

Clause structure and movement constraints in Russian. In Claudia Corum, T. Cedric Smith-Stark & Ann Weiser (eds.): *You take the high node and I'll take the low node: Papers from the Comparative Syntax Festival*, 291–304. Chicago: Chicago Linguistic Society.

[Reprinted 1980 in Catherine V. Chvany & Richard D. Brecht (eds.): *Morphosyntax in Slavic*, 98–113. Columbus, OH: Slavica.]

The ergative: variations on a theme. *Lingua* 32: 239–253.

Синтаксис и семантика в трансформационной генеративной грамматике. [Syntax and semantics in transformational generative grammar.] In S.K. Šaumjan (ed.): *Проблемы структурной лингвистики 1972*, 543–554. Moscow: Nauka.

1974

Impersonal subjects in Russian. *Foundations of Language* 12: 103–115.

Order and tell in a transformational grammar of English. *Studia Anglica Posnaniensia* 5: 3–8.

The second dative: a transformational approach. In Richard D. Brecht and Catherine V. Chvany (eds.): *Slavic transformational syntax* (Michigan Slavic Materials 10), 123–150. Ann Arbor: Department of Slavic Languages and Literatures, University of Michigan.

[Reprinted 1977.]

Transformationsanalyse russischer Nominalisierungen. [Transformational analysis of Russian nominalizations.] In G. Freidhof (ed.): *Notizen und Materialien zur russischen Linguistik, Unterlagen für die Seminararbeit* (Specimina Philologiae Slavicae 6), 38–46. Frankfurt am Main; distr. by Kubon & Sagner, Munich.

[English translation: Nominalizations in Russian: lexical noun phrases or transformed sentences?, in Catherine V. Chvany & Richard D. Brecht (eds.): *Morphosyntax in Slavic*, 212–220, Columbus, OH: Slavica, 1980.

Russian translation: Номинализация в русском языке: словарно задаваемые именные группы или трансформированные предложения. *Новое в зарубежной лингвистике* 15: 42–49, Moscow: Progress, 1985.]

1975

The antiergative: Finland's answer to Basque. *Chicago Linguistic Society* 11: 112–121.

Causatives and universal grammar. *Transactions of the Philological Society* 1974: 1–32.

Common (?) Slavonic **sedmъ*. *Slavonic and East European Review* 53: 323–329.

Cosmonauts and astronauts. *Association of Teachers of Russian Newsletter*, October 1975: 4.

(under pseudonym Émil Schouwiniste-Pigge) On being polite to women in Slavic languages. *Pragmatics Microfiche* 1.3: 1–3.

[Reprinted in T. Ernst & E. Smith (eds.): *Son of Lingua Franca*, 5–6. Bloomington: Indiana University Linguistics Club, 1979.]

Polite plurals and predicate agreement. *Language* 51: 406–418.

1976

Archaisms in nineteenth-century Russian literature. *Journal of Russian Studies* 32: 36–39.

Irregular stress in Polish and Macedonian. *International Review of Slavic Linguistics* 1: 227–240.

Linguistic politeness axes: speaker–addressee, speaker–referent, speaker–bystander. *Pragmatics Microfiche* 1.7: A3 (12 pp.).

The syntax of action nominals: a cross-language study. *Lingua* 40: 177–201.

The syntax of causative constructions: cross-language similarities and divergences. In Masayoshi Shibatani (ed.): *The grammar of causative constructions* (Syntax and Semantics 6), 261–312. New York: Academic Press.

1977

In defense of spontaneous demotion: the impersonal passive. In Peter Cole & Jerrold M. Sadock (eds.): *Grammatical relations* (Syntax and Semantics 8), 47–58. New York: Academic Press.

(Edward L. Keenan, Bernard Comrie) Noun phrase accessibility and universal grammar. *Linguistic Inquiry* 8, 63–99.

[Russian translation: Иерархия доступности именных групп и универсальная грамматика, in A. E. Kibrik (comp.): *Новое в зарубежной лингвистике, выпуск XI: Современные синтаксические теории в американской лингвистике*, 111–165. Moscow, Progress, 1982.]

‘Subjects and direct objects in Uralic languages: a functional explanation of case-marking systems’. *Études Finno-Ougriennes* 12 (1975): 5–17.

1978

Definite direct objects and referent identification. *Pragmatics Microfiche* 3.1: D3 (20 pp.).

Ergativity. In Winfred P. Lehmann (ed.): *Syntactic typology: Studies in the phenomenology of language*, 329–394. Austin: University of Texas Press.

Genitive–accusatives in Slavic: the rules and their motivation. In Bernard Comrie (ed.): *Classification of grammatical categories* (Current Inquiry into Language and Linguistics, 21, Slavic Series, 6; also = *International Journal of Slavic Linguistics* 3.1–2), 37–42. Edmonton: Linguistic Research.

Linguistics is about languages. In Braj B. Kachru (ed.): *Linguistics in the seventies: Directions and prospects* (= *Studies in the Linguistic Sciences* 8.2), 221–236. Urbana: University of Illinois, Department of Linguistics.

Morphological classification of cases in the Slavonic languages. *Slavonic and East European Review* 56: 177–191.

On the *go* ~ *went* alternation: a contribution (?) to the generative phonology of English. In T. Ernst & E. Smith (eds.): *Lingua Franca*, 59–63. Bloomington: Indiana University Linguistics Club. [Electronic version: <http://specgram.com/LP/31.comrie.gowent.html>]

1979

The animacy hierarchy in Chukchee. In Paul R. Clyne, William F. Hanks & Carol L. Hofbauer (eds.): *The elements: A parasession on linguistic units and levels, Including Papers from the Conference on Non-Slavic Languages of the USSR*, 322–329. Chicago: Chicago Linguistic Society.

(Edward L. Keenan, Bernard Comrie) Data on the noun phrase accessibility hierarchy. *Language* 55: 333–351.

Definite and animate direct objects: a natural class. *Linguistica Silesiana* 3: 13–21.

Degrees of ergativity: some Chukchee evidence. In Frans Plank (ed.): *Ergativity: Towards a theory of grammatical relations*, 219–240. London: Academic Press.

Morphophonemic exceptions and phonetic distance. *Linguistics* 17: 51–60.

(Bernard Comrie, Edward L. Keenan) Noun phrase accessibility revisited. *Language* 55: 649–64.

On being further tempted from *go* to *went*. In T. Ernst & E. Smith (eds.): *Son of Lingua Franca*, 5–6. Bloomington: Indiana University Linguistics Club.

On the bases of syntactic reanalysis. *Buffalo Papers in Linguistics* 1.3: 85–110.

Russian. In Timothy Shopen (ed.): *Languages and their status*, 91–151. Cambridge, MA: Winthrop.

[Reprinted: Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 1987.]

Some remarks on ergativity in South Asian languages. *South Asian Language Analysis* 1: 211–219.

1980

Agreement, animacy, and voice. In Gunter Brettschneider & Christian Lehmann (eds.): *Wege zur Universalienforschung: Sprachwissenschaftliche Beiträge zum 60. Geburtstag von Hansjakob Seiler* (Tübinger Beiträge zur Linguistik 145), 229–234. Tübingen: Gunter Narr.

Diachronic arguments for the psychological reality of abstract phonology: a critical review. In Brian Butterworth (ed.): *Language production*, volume 1: *Speech and talk*, 271–296. London: Academic Press.

The genetic affiliation of Kamchadal: some morphological evidence. *International Review of Slavic Linguistics* 5: 109–120.

[This volume also appeared as Bernard Comrie (ed.): *Studies in the languages of the USSR*. (Current Inquiry into Language, Linguistics and Human Communication 38). Edmonton: Linguistic Research, 1981; reprinted 1987 *PIL* 16/3–4: 109–120.]

Inverse verb forms in Siberia: evidence from Chukchee, Koryak, and Kamchadal. *Folia Linguistica Historica* 1: 61–74.

Morphology and word order reconstruction: problems and prospects. In Jacek Fisiak (ed.): *Historical morphology* (Trends in Linguistics, Studies and Monographs 17), 83–96. The Hague: Mouton.

[Reprinted in *Mouton Classics*, 359–372. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter, 2002.]

The order of case and possessive suffixes in Uralic languages: an approach to the comparative-historical problem. *Lingua Posnaniensis* 23 (= *In honorem Ceslai Kudzinowski*): 81–86.

The sun letters in Maltese: between morphophonemics and phonetics. In Michael Kenstowicz (ed.), *Studies in Arabic linguistics* (= *Studies in the Linguistic Sciences* 10.2), 25–37. Urbana: University of Illinois, Department of Linguistics.

1981

Aspect and voice: some reflections on perfect and passive. In Philip J. Tedeschi & Annie Zaenen (eds.): *Tense and aspect* (Syntax and Semantics 14), 65–78. New York: Academic Press.

(Larry M. Hyman, Bernard Comrie) Coreference and logophoricity in Gokana. In William R. Leben (ed.): *Précis from the 12th Conference on African linguistics, Stanford, April 10-12, 1981*. (= *Studies in African Linguistics, Suppl.* 8), 69–73. Los Angeles: Dept. of Linguistics, University of California.

Direct object case-marking in Uralic languages: an explanatory model. In Gyula Ortutay (ed.): *Congressus Quartus Internationalis Fenno-Ugristarum Budapestini habitus 9.–15. Septembris 1975*, Pars III: *Acta Sectionis Linguisticae* (ed. Gábor Bereczki, János Gulya), 265–269. Budapest: Akadémiai Kiadó.

Ergativity and grammatical relations in Kalaw Lagaw Ya (Saibai dialect). *Australian Journal of Linguistics* 1: 1–42.

The formation of relative clauses. In Barbara Lloyd & John Gay (eds.): *Universals of human thought: Some African evidence*, 215–233. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

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Negation and other verb categories in the Uralic languages. In Osmo Ikola (ed.): *Congressus Quintus Internationalis Fenno-Ugristarum, Pars VI: Dissertationes sectionum: Phonologica et morphologica, syntactica et semantica*, 350–355. Turku: Suomen Kielen Seura.

On Reichenbach's approach to tense. *Chicago Linguistic Society* 17: 24–30.

The theoretical significance of the Latin accusative and infinitive: a reply to Pillinger. *Journal of Linguistics* 17: 345–349.

1982

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Grammatical relations in Huichol. In Paul J. Hopper & Sandra A. Thompson (eds.): *Studies in transitivity*. (Syntax and Semantics 15), 95–115. New York: Academic Press.

On the morphological typology of Balto-Finnic: a reassessment. *Études Finno-Ougriennes* 15: 91–99.

Remarks on clitic-climbing in Brazilian Portuguese. *Lingua* 58: 243–265.

Syntactic–morphological discrepancies in Maltese sentence structure. *Communication and Cognition* 15: 281–306.

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Verb agreement in Ket. *Folia Slavica* 5: 115–127.

1983

On the validity of typological studies: a reply to Smith. *Australian Journal of Linguistics* 3: 93–98.

Switch-reference in Huichol: a typological study. In John Haiman & Pamela Munro (eds.): *Switch-reference and universal grammar* (Typological Studies in Language 2), 17–37. Amsterdam: John Benjamins. <https://doi.org/10.1075/tsl.2.04com>

1984

Agreement as a research tool. *Proceedings of the First Eastern States Conference on Linguistics*, 13–26. Columbus: Ohio State University.

Explanation in language typology. *Cadernos de Estudos Lingüísticos* (Universidade Estadual de Campinas, Instituto de Estudos da Linguagem, Campinas, Brazil) 6: 59–70.

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(Bernard Comrie, Heather Holmback) The future subjunctive in Portuguese: a problem in semantic theory. *Lingua* 63: 213–253.

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Reflections on verb agreement in Hindi and related languages. *Linguistics* 22: 857–864.

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